

Adaptive Wave and Path Generation in Tower Defense Games

Abstract

This research explores the implementation of adaptive wave and path generation in Tower Defense (TD) games, focusing on the depth-first search (DFS) algorithm for map generation and a weight-based wave generation system. The objective is to create engaging and dynamic gameplay that adapts to players' strategies and performance. By incorporating elements such as secondary path generation and adaptive difficulty, this work aims to address common challenges in game design, such as unpredictability and scalability, thereby enhancing player experience and strategic depth.

Introduction

Tower Defense games have gained immense popularity due to their strategic gameplay and challenging mechanics. However, maintaining player engagement over multiple levels often requires innovative approaches to difficulty scaling and path generation. As players progress, they seek both challenges that test their skills and elements that keep the

gameplay fresh and exciting. This research presents a system that combines DFS for map generation with a weight-based algorithm for enemy wave progression, creating a dynamic gameplay experience that adapts to player performance. Through effective wave management and strategic pathing, players are encouraged to develop diverse tactics, enhancing the overall engagement of the game.

Related Work

Previous research has examined procedural generation techniques in game design, such as tile-based map generation and algorithmic difficulty adjustment (Shaker et al., 2016; Togelius et al., 2013). Existing studies have focused on various aspects of game development, including user experience, AI behavior, and balance in gameplay mechanics. However, many existing systems lack a comprehensive integration of pathfinding and wave generation. This paper builds upon these foundations by introducing a cohesive framework that combines both elements to create a more engaging and adaptive TD experience.

Moreover, the advancement of AI and machine learning technologies presents opportunities for further exploration in adaptive gameplay mechanics, allowing for even more nuanced and responsive enemy behaviors that can adjust in real-time based on player actions.

Core Algorithm

Map Generation

The core algorithm employs a DFS technique with additional features to support dynamic difficulty adjustment and secondary path generation. The map is represented as a 2D grid, where cells can be classified as walls or paths, ensuring a clear structure for the gameplay experience.

DFS Technique

In the tower defense game, the Depth-First Search (DFS) algorithm plays a crucial role in generating paths for both the main and secondary enemy spawn points. DFS is used to explore the maze-like grid, starting from the origin (start point), by visiting as many cells as possible before backtracking. This ensures that paths are extended deeply into the maze before connecting to endpoints. For secondary spawn points, the DFS ensures connections to the main path without intersecting previously visited nodes, maintaining path integrity. This method allows efficient path generation while balancing exploration with backtracking to optimize spawn point placement.

Depth First Search Technique

Initialization

The map dimensions are determined based on the current level, considering factors such as player progress and overall game pacing. Arrays and collections are initialized to track

visited cells, wall positions, and props, setting the foundation for the procedural generation process.

Map Structure and Path Generation

A stack-based DFS approach is utilized to carve out the map paths. The randomized selection of neighbors ensures varied map structures, while target vertices are dynamically adjusted based on the total number of blocks and the current level. This randomness not only promotes unpredictability but also encourages players to adapt their strategies continuously.

Secondary Path Generation

Every 15 levels, a secondary path containing an enemy spawn point at one end is introduced to increase complexity. This generation process ensures no overlap with primary or secondary paths, enhancing the unpredictability of enemy movement. These secondary paths serve to challenge players' tactical decisions, encouraging them to allocate resources strategically to address threats emerging from unexpected directions.

Terrains and Props

Random props are placed on walls, avoiding start and end points. Terrain-specific troops are introduced to add diversity to gameplay. Different terrain types can have varying effects on troop movement and enemy behavior, requiring players to consider environmental factors in their strategic planning. Water layers can serve as boundaries for the map, creating distinct areas that enhance gameplay complexity.

Wave Generation Algorithm

The wave generation in this Tower Defense game is based on the total weight of enemies before generation, augmented by a base weight influenced by difficulty.

Weight Calculation

The formula for calculating the current wave's weight is as follows:

$$Cw = \{Bw + (GC * St * n) - C\} \cdot D$$

Where:

- **Current Weight (Cw):** The weight assigned to the current wave.
- **Base Weight (Bw):** The initial weight representing the fundamental difficulty level.
- **Difficulty (D):** A multiplier that scales the wave's weight based on the game's difficulty.
- **Current Maximum Sum of the Portion of the Path Covered by Every Troop (St):** The maximum cumulative measure of the path covered by all troops.
- **Total Game Currency (GC):** The currency received until the current level for troop placement and upgrades.
- **Temporary Compensation (C):** A constant value subtracted to balance the wave's weight based on the player's previous level performance.
- **Punishment (P):** A value added to negate temporary compensation progressively.
- **Normalizing Factor (n):** A constant that normalizes the weight based on individual enemy weight.

This weight-based system ensures that each wave poses an appropriate challenge, balancing player capabilities with game difficulty.

Troop Detection, Attack, and Determination of St

Detection

The Army unit script detects enemies within a specified radius, filtering for tagged enemies. A* pathfinding ensures the unit targets the closest enemy, allowing for efficient targeting and resource allocation.

Attack

The attack mechanism involves shooting at the closest enemy within the detection radius, incorporating cooldown periods to manage troop efficiency. This mechanic ensures that units remain active and engaged, promoting strategic positioning and timing.

Determining Portion of Path Covered

A grid-based approach calculates the area covered by the Army unit within the detection radius, contributing to a global tracker for adaptive wave generation. This tracking system

allows for adjustments in wave generation, responding to troop positioning and overall strategy.

A* Algorithm

The A* algorithm is a critical component in the game's pathfinding system, allowing for efficient identification of the shortest routes between points, particularly for targeting enemies or navigating the maze-like game environment. A* combines both the actual cost from the start node to a given node (known as the *g-cost*) and a heuristic estimate of the remaining distance to the target (known as the *h-cost*), striking an optimal balance between exploring nodes with the lowest cost and those closest to the goal. This results in a more informed search compared to traditional algorithms like Dijkstra or Greedy Best-First Search.

In the context of the tower defense game, A* pathfinding enables dynamic and intelligent enemy movement, as it ensures that enemies select the most efficient path toward objectives, such as towers or player defenses. This not only enhances the realism and challenge of enemy behavior but also introduces strategic depth for players. By predicting the paths that enemies are likely to take, players can place defenses more effectively, anticipate high-traffic areas, and adapt to enemy movement patterns. The integration of A* not only improves the overall game experience by creating intelligent AI but also deepens player engagement through its impact on strategic decision-making.

A Star Algorithm

Challenges Addressed

The path generation and wave algorithms developed address several key challenges in Tower Defense games:

- **Unpredictability:** Randomized path generation enhances the unpredictability of enemy movement, promoting strategic adaptation each level.
- **Scalability:** The weight-based system ensures progressive difficulty, maintaining challenge without overwhelming players.
- **Adaptivity:** The algorithms adapt to player performance, dynamically adjusting difficulty based on successes or failures.

In addition, these systems can help mitigate common player frustrations associated with repetitive gameplay by introducing new challenges and requiring players to adapt their strategies continually.

Conclusion

This research presents a sophisticated system for path and wave generation in Tower Defense games. By incorporating DFS for path generation and a weight-based algorithm for enemy waves, the gameplay remains engaging and strategic. The additional complexity of secondary paths and adaptive difficulty enhances the player experience, creating a game environment that evolves with the player's skill level. Future iterations could explore procedural terrain generation or more complex enemy behaviors, further enriching gameplay and replayability. The findings suggest that integrating advanced procedural generation techniques can significantly enhance player engagement and satisfaction, making this an exciting area for further exploration in game design.

References

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